

PAM 43.675 frag. 4 = Lev 4:29-31: Another Cave 4 Leviticus Manuscript?

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One of the many hitherto unidentified fragments from Qumran Cave 4, PAM 43.675 frag. 4¹ (see now the new photographs on the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Electronic Library²) may be identified textually with Lev 4:29-31. One should read the preserved traces on the fragment somewhat differently from the transcription of the editors. Rather, the fragment reads as follows

Transcription

יִדְּוֹ עַל רֹאשׁ	1
קָרְנֵי וְזֶבַח הָעֹלֹת	2
חֲלָבִים מִעֵל	3

Reading

In line 2, the *qof* is not certain; the few traces which may be remnants of *qof* could also be spots of ink. Both in line 2 and in line 3, the only remaining trace of *ayin* is the top of the right stroke.

Textual Identification

The phrase *ידו על ראש* (את) *וסמך* followed in the next verse by *קרנת מזבח העלה* and subsequently one verse later by *חלב* is attested in Lev 4:24-26, 4:29-31, and 4:33-35. However, the probable *mem* after *חלב* in line 3 only fits Lev 4:31.

A full reconstruction of the missing parts of the lines according to the Masoretic text results in lines of ca. 16 words (reconstruction according to the Samaritan text would differ only in details), e.g.,

[וסמך את יִדְּוֹ עַל רֹאשׁ הַחֲטָאת וְשַׁחֲטָהּ אֶת הַחֲטָאת בַּמָּקוֹם הָעֹלֹת וְלָקַח הַכֹּהֵן מִדָּמָהּ בְּאֶזְבֵּעֵו]	1
[וְנָתַן עַל קָרְנֵי וְזֶבַח הָעֹלֹת וְאֵת כָּל דָּמָהּ יִשְׁפֹךְ אֶל יְסוֹד הַמִּזְבֵּחַ וְאֵת כָּל חֲלָבֶיהָ יִסִּיר כְּאֲשֶׁר]	2
[הוֹסֵר חֲלָבִים מִעֵל זֶבַח הַשְּׁלָמִים וְהַקְטִיר הַכֹּהֵן הַמִּזְבֵּחַ לְרִיחַ נִיחַח לַיהוָה וְכִפֵּר עָלָיו הַכֹּהֵן וְנִסְלַח]	3

¹DJD 33, plate XVI and <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285454>.

²<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-494861>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-494862>

Material and Scribal Features

The fragment has many spots of ink. The letters are relatively small (0.2 cm) and the distance between the lines is ca. 0.7 mm. Horizontal guide lines are clear in line 2 and much more faint in line 3. Very few letters are completely preserved, but the hand could be Herodian, or, perhaps more likely, late Hasmonaean. The typical features of the Herodian bookhand are not attested. For example *zayin* does not have the thickening of the top. Also less typical of the Herodian script is the difference in size of the letters in the word מִזְבֵּחַ, with a large *mem*, and a relatively small *zayin* and *bet*. Note also that the apparent curve of the downstroke of the *bet* into the basestroke is (and similarly in *mem*) are more typical of the Hasmonaean than of the Herodian bookhand. Spaces in between the words are about the width of one letter.

Manuscript Identification

Can one identify the fragment as belonging to any of the published Qumran Cave 4 Leviticus fragments? Script and spacing between lines are entirely different from 4Q17 (4QExod-Lev^f) and 4Q23 (4QLev-Num^a) which have much earlier hands. The script is likewise different from that of the two manuscripts formerly incorrectly joined together as 4Q24, both of which have an earlier Hasmonaean hand.³ 4Q25 has a typical Herodian bookhand, its columns are much narrower, and the distance between the lines is smaller. 4Q26 has an entirely different leather (affected by corrosion of the ink). There is some correspondence with 4Q26a, especially 4Q26a frags. 1-2 (Lev 3:2-4 and 5-8), which has lines of similar length, the same distance between the lines, and frag. 1 has, similarly to PAM 43.675 frag. 4, many spots of ink. However, in virtually every letter form there are small differences. One might contrast most easily 4Q26a 1 line 3 לַע with PAM 43.675 frag. 4 line 1 לַע. Finally, the preservation of the material and the script of 4Q26b are entirely different. For the record, the fragments does not match either any of the Leviticus from other Qumran Caves.

A comparison with the Reworked Pentateuch manuscripts shows it is closest with respect to hand and appearance to 4Q158, but there too the way of writing לַע and details of the forms of letters are different.

In short, it is unlikely that this fragment derives from any of the published Qumran Cave 4 Leviticus manuscripts. It is therefore most likely the sole remnants of yet another Cave 4 Leviticus fragment. One might want to number it 4Q26c, which, unfortunately, had been given by Emile Puech to Schøyen MS 4011.⁴ However, in view of the problems of 4Q24, which consists of fragments of certainly two, and possibly three different manuscripts, one would rather await a wholesale renumbering of the Cave 4 Leviticus manuscripts.

³Eibert Tigchelaar, "Reconsidering 4Q24 (4QLeviticus^b): Two Manuscripts and a New Fragment." *Vetus Testamentum* 71 (2021): 263-73.

⁴Emile Puech, "Un autre manuscrit du *Lévitique*." *Revue de Qumran* 21/82 (2003): 311-13.